

Experimental Characterization of the AA7075 Aluminum Alloy using Hot Shear Tensile Test

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Keywords: Shear tensile test, AA7075 alloy, dynamic recrystallization, large strain, edge effect

Abstract. The understanding of the material behavior under shear loading has great importance for a researcher in manufacturing processes like cutting, machining, milling, turning, friction stir welding, etc. where the material experiences large deformation at high temperature. For such material behavior analysis, hot shear tests provide a useful means to investigate the evolution of the microstructure at a wide range of temperature and to improve the material behavior model. Shear tests can be performed by direct shear loading (e.g. torsion of thin-walled tubular samples), or appropriate specimen design to convert a tensile or compressive load into shear (e.g. simple shear tests). The simple shear tests are straightforward. However, the design of a specimen is not so simple, and it is also difficult to obtain a very large deformation. In addition, the existing design of the specimen for the simple shear tests are concerned only with the elastic response of the material. It is becoming increasingly important to capture a plastic response of the material. Plastic deformation is significantly more complex and is known to depend more heavily on the strain rate, temperature, deformation, etc. Besides, there is not enough work is done on high-temperature shear testing. The objective of this study is to design a new tensile-shear specimen geometry to convert the tensile load into the dominant shear load in high-temperature tests in order to study the plastic behavior of the material. The specimen geometry design is based on the Finite Element Method (FEM). The material used in this article is aluminum alloy (AA7075), which is tested quasi statically under elevated temperature. Finally, the microstructural changes that take place during plastic deformation are studied using an optical microscope.